

Electrodeposited NiCoP cathode catalyst for alkaline membrane water electrolysis

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Phosphide-based materials are among the favourable catalysts due to their promising properties (catalytic activity, stability, and electrical conductivity) for hydrogen evolution reaction in both alkaline and acidic media. This study reports on preparation and subsequent characterisation of a non-platinum NiCoP catalyst for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) using facile cathodic electrodeposition on a Ni support without toxic phosphorising agents. In the first step, catalyst synthesis optimisation was performed by monitoring the effect of (i) Ni:Co composition and (ii) phosphorus concentration in the deposition solution. Impact of these parameters on the composition as well as the HER electrocatalytic activity of the resulting catalyst was evaluated. Subsequently, the optimised NiCoP catalyst deposited on Ni foam was used as cathode for the HER in an alkaline membrane water electrolyser. It exhibited significant catalytic activity and excellent stability. In summary, the cathodic electrodeposition proved to be a feasible method for producing an active and stable NiCoP catalyst for the HER in an alkaline media.

Introduction

Alkaline water electrolysis (AWE) is an industrially well-established technology that has yet again started to draw a lot of attention mainly due to new findings in the field of materials science. Significant advances in the development of new anion-selective polymer electrolytes and more active electrocatalysts made it possible to address current main drawbacks of this technology, i.e., low current densities and flexibility^{1,2}. The so-called alkaline membrane water electrolysis (AMWE) technology deals with these limitations by combining the advantages of industrial AWE and proton-exchange membrane electrolysis (PEMWE)³:

- (i) The polymer electrolyte membrane with intrinsic ionic conductivity allows using a zero-gap arrangement and, thus, a less concentrated KOH solution. This further improves flexibility of the process.
- (ii) The zero-gap arrangement enables the AMWE to operate at higher current densities and thus with higher intensity than AWE.
- (iii) Unlike in PEMWE, where only platinum group metals (PGM) can be used as catalyst for stability reasons, the alkaline or weakly alkaline environment of AMWE is suitable for a large number of materials with reasonable chemical

stability and electrocatalytic activity for hydrogen (HER), as well as oxygen evolution reaction (OER).

In the case of HER, a vast number of materials based on alloys, selenides, nitrides, and most recently phosphides have already been reported to achieve comparable and, frequently, even superior performance to the state-of-the-art Pt catalysts⁴⁻⁷. In general, transition-metal phosphides (TMPs) exhibit promising properties for catalysing HER (e.g., catalytic activity, stability, and electrical conductivity) in both acidic and alkaline media^{8,9}. The phosphorus enhances the catalytic activity of the material by weakening the H–OH bond in water, which facilitates water dissociation¹⁰. Moreover, according to Eftekari¹¹, the reaction proceeds along the basal crystal plane, not just at the sites of crystal edges as is the case for metal sulfides and selenides. Besides, owing to a wide range of viable structures and compositions, it is possible to modify the physico-chemical properties of TMPs and thus to achieve desirable electrocatalytic activity, stability, and electronic conductivity of the materials. To illustrate, the most active and stable HER catalysts (e.g., NiFeCoP/Ni mesh¹² and CoMoP¹³) are able to achieve HER current density of -10 mA cm^{-2} at overpotentials as low as -30 mV surpassing the state-of-the-art platinum catalysts (with corresponding overpotential of $\approx -40 \text{ mV}$)¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Nevertheless, extensive utilisation of TMPs in the industry is hindered mainly by limited stability and complex or even potentially dangerous synthesis procedures^{7,17}. These commonly include application of flammable or toxic phosphorising reagents, or high reaction temperatures¹⁸. Sometimes a rigorously inert atmosphere is required^{18,19}. Some methods utilise even an in-situ decomposition of inorganic sources of phosphorous to produce gaseous and highly toxic PH_3 acting as a phosphorising agent^{19,20}. This brings additional

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challenges in terms of operation safety and exhaust post-treatment.

Cathodic electrochemical deposition is a facile and efficient technique capable of producing desired materials at mild conditions¹⁹. In 1998, Djokic²¹ investigated the electrodeposition of amorphous alloys based on iron group metals. He managed to prepare the Ni, Co, and NiCoP compounds with an amorphous or nanocrystalline structure. However, a H_3PO_3 was used as a source of phosphorous, which does not meet the current requirements for the preferable use of harmless substances. Other electrodeposition method based on less hazardous hypophosphites has been successfully utilised to produce highly catalytically active and stable catalysts²²⁻²⁵. The electrodeposited Ni-P/Ni foam exhibited excellent activity (HER overpotential of -30 mV at -10 mA cm^{-2} in 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH) and good long-term stability²². Similar results were achieved with the electrodeposited CoP mesoporous nanorod arrays on Ni foam. The catalyst exhibited high bifunctional activity for HER and OER (overpotentials of -54 mV and $+290$ mV at ± 10 mA cm^{-2} , respectively) and sufficient stability²³.

Elemental doping proved to be a feasible strategy to enhance the catalytic activity, stability, and electronic conductivity by optimising the electronic structure as well as synergistic effects between the transition metals^{6, 10, 26, 27}. From the ternary TMPs, the NiCo-based phosphides rank among the most active materials. According to Zang et al.¹⁰, the Ni atoms accelerate water dissociation, whereas Co atoms boost the recombination of H atoms and desorption of produced H_2 . The properties of the NiCoP catalyst can thus be influenced by the amount of phosphorus and by the ratio of Ni and Co in the material²⁸.

Electrodeposition of the NiCoP layer is much less common in literature when compare to the in-situ growth of TMPs on appropriate substrate involving typically two steps: deposition of the precursors and following phosphidisation²⁹. The reason may lie in the fact that electrodeposition process is quite complex and many parameters can affect the composition and thus activity of the prepared catalyst. In principle, it is possible to find two types of reports in an open literature. First type is focused on the electrodeposition of the transition metal phosphides under different conditions following their effect on the material final composition^{21, 30}. However, the effect of deposition conditions on HER activity is not evaluated. The second group of reports studies HER activity of transition metal phosphides prepared by the electrochemical deposition, but study on the deposition conditions is missing³¹⁻³⁴. This work aims on filling this gap by identification and characterisation of the catalyst providing best performance for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) by monitoring the effect of (i) Ni:Co ratio and (ii) PO_2H_2^- concentration in the deposition solution.

Beyond the scope of previous works, performance of the optimised NiCoP catalyst deposited on Ni foam for the HER was determined in an alkaline membrane water electrolyser. In order to understand into the more detail behaviour observed, distribution of the relaxation times analysis of electrochemical impedance data was performed. It helped to discover number of time constants and their characteristic frequencies. This is an important aspect, as impedance spectra analysis currently reported in the literature are usually based on PEM water electrolysis experience. They thus do not reflect differences in the electrode reactions mechanism. Identifying valid equivalent electrical circuit, kinetic data for both, anode and cathode reaction were evaluated under the conditions of the alkaline water electrolysis.

To the best of our knowledge, such complex analysis showing several aspects of the NiCoP catalyst synthesis on the properties of the catalyst, results under the conditions of the alkaline water electrolysis supported by electrochemical impedance analysis is missing in the literature, although it represents crucial step in efficient utilisation of this material in an industrial practice.

Experimental part

Catalyst preparation and characterisation

The NiCoP catalyst was synthesised by cathodic electrodeposition (-25 mA cm^{-2} , 15 min) on the surface of the Ni plate (5×4 cm^2) at 25 °C. A three-electrode arrangement was used in order to track the progress of the electrode potential over time. A mercury mercurous sulphate electrode in saturated K_2SO_4 (sat. Hg / Hg_2SO_4) and an activated titanium electrode served as a reference and counter electrode, respectively. The deposition solution contained $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a source of Ni and Co, and $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ as a source of phosphorous. The concentrations of $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.3 , 0.6 , 0.9 , and 1.2 mol dm^{-3}) and total concentration of Ni, Co salts 0.4 mol dm^{-3} with different Ni:Co compositions (0 , 0.1 , 0.25 , 0.5 , 0.75 , 0.9) were used. The deposited layer was scraped off and grinded in ethanol in a laboratory Mini Mill (15 min, oscillation 30 s^{-1}) using ZrO_2 milling vessel and balls. The powdered catalyst was used for subsequent structural and electrochemical characterisations. Because of significant number of the samples prepared, the composition of the deposition solutions is summarized in [Table 1](#). For clarity, the samples are referred as $x\text{Ni}_y\text{Co}_z\text{P}$ with x , y , z showing the concentration of the $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively in the synthesis solution.

ARTICLE

Table 1: Composition of the solutions for the $x\text{Ni}_y\text{Co}_z\text{P}$ catalyst deposition.

Optimisation step	Ni:Co composition	Concentration (mol dm^{-3})		
		$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
NaPO ₂ H ₂ ·H ₂ O concentration	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.3
NaPO ₂ H ₂ ·H ₂ O concentration	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.6
NaPO ₂ H ₂ ·H ₂ O concentration	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.9
NaPO ₂ H ₂ ·H ₂ O concentration	0.5	0.2	0.2	1.2
Ni:Co composition	0	0	0.4	0.6
Ni:Co composition	0.05	0.02	0.038	0.6
Ni:Co composition	0.1	0.04	0.36	0.6
Ni:Co composition	0.25	0.1	0.3	0.6
Ni:Co composition	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.6
Ni:Co composition	0.75	0.3	0.1	0.6
Ni:Co composition	0.9	0.36	0.04	0.6

The elemental composition of the prepared samples was determined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Hitachi S4700, Japan) equipped with an EDX analyser and by an X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectrometer Axios (PANalytical, Holland). The structure and morphology were observed by a scanning electron microscope (Hitachi S4700, Japan) and a transmission electron microscope (TEM and HRTEM, JEM-2100F, JEOL, Japan, equipped with an INCA X-ray microanalysis system). The surface area was evaluated from the BET isotherms (Quantachrome Instruments, USA).

The X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) experiments involved the study of the as-prepared samples to identify the composition of the surface layer. Measurements of XPS spectra were performed on SPECS Phoibos 150 hemispherical analyser (Germany) using non-monochromatic Mg ($h\nu = 1253.6$ eV) radiation. Survey scans were measured with resolution of 1 eV and pass energy of 40 eV. Detailed scans (C 1s, O 1s, Ni 2p, Co 2p, P 2p) were measured with resolution of 0.05 eV and pass energy of 20 eV. Binding energies were corrected using the main adventitious carbon sp^3 peak located at 284.9 eV while the C 1s spectrum was deconvoluted using procedure recommended by Biesinger³⁵. The corresponding corrections varied between 3.0 and 4.9 eV, suggesting medium surface charging. Due to this surface charging and application of non-monochromatised X-ray, the high-resolution spectra were measured in binding energy regions of 894–840 eV for Ni 2p, 815–760 eV for Co 2p and 144–125 eV for phosphorous 2p, 541–528 eV for O1s, 282–295 eV for C 1s. Spectra deconvolution was performed using KolXPD software. A Shirley type background was used in all cases. All 2p peaks were fitted using a Voigt

doublets with the ratio of 2:1 for corresponding $p_{3/2}:p_{1/2}$ components. Satellites and Auger peaks (present in the case of Co 2p) were approximated by individual Voigt functions. Finally, due to application of non-monochromatised Mg K α X-ray radiation, presence of X-ray satellites (α_3 and α_4) for each main core-level peak in Co 2p and Ni 2p and P 2p detailed spectra had to be considered. Each α_3 (α_4) satellite is shifted by 8.4 eV (10.1 eV) to lower binding energy with respect to the main core-level peak and its intensity is 8% (4%) of the same. In order to reduce number of optimised parameters during deconvolution to reasonable level, all other parameters of these X-ray satellites were set to be the same as parameters of the main core-level peak.

Electrocatalytic activity was determined using a rotating disk electrode (RDE) at 25 °C in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KOH solution saturated by N₂. Galvanostatic arrangement was used. The current densities used ranged from 0 to -10 mA cm^{-2} with a current scan rate of 10 $\mu\text{A s}^{-1}$ (50 $\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). Ni wire and reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) were used as a counter and reference electrode, respectively. The revolution rate of the disk electrode was set to 500 rpm to ensure a removal of the H₂ bubbles formed. A catalyst ink contained 10 mg of the powdered catalyst, 10 μl of an anion-selective binder Fumion (8–12 wt.% in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone) homogeneously dispersed in 5 ml of water. A total volume of 2×10 μl of the ink was pipetted onto the glassy carbon RDE (0.196 cm^2) in two steps. Each drop was allowed to dry (freely in the air) before proceeding further. After the solvents evaporated, the electrode was ready for measurements. Prior to the actual measurement, the electrodes were activated/stabilised by 100 galvanostatic cycles

(between 0 to -10 mA cm^{-2} using a current density scan rate of $50 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). For each sample, three RDEs were measured; the results show averaged values. Electrochemical activity of the powdery samples was determined from the analysis of polarisation curves by the Tafel analysis (Tafel slope and overpotential at current densities of -10 mA cm^{-2}). For comparison purposes, RDEs with phosphide based catalyst and RDE with Pt/C (40 wt. %, Johnson-Matthey, UK) were used.

Cathode material for membrane alkaline water electrolysis

The cathode containing the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ catalyst was prepared by direct electrodeposition on the Ni foam under the same conditions as described in paragraph **Chyba! Nenalezen zdroj odkazů..** Electrodes are then referred as $\text{xNi}_y\text{Co}_z\text{P}/\text{NF}$. The catalyst loading was determined by weighing the dried electrode. For comparison purposes, (i) bare Ni foam (INCO Advanced Technology Materials (Dalian) Co., Ltd, $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$, pore size $580 \mu\text{m}$) and (ii) Ni foam modified by a Pt/C (40 wt. %, Johnson-Matthey, UK) catalyst ($0.4 \text{ mg Pt cm}^{-2}$) fixed to the substrate by an poly(styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene) copolymer (PSEBS) with 1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane (DABCO) functional groups anion-selective binder ($0.08 \text{ mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm}^{-2}$) were used as cathodes. PSEBS-DABCO polymer was used instead of Fumion binder due to the better compatibility of the PSEBS-DABCO binder with electrode separator. Pt/C catalyst layer was deposited on the Ni foam electrode using sonication dispersion deposition method from catalyst ink containing catalyst, binder and solvent/dispersant (chloroform). Catalyst ink was sonicated for 30 minutes in sonication bath prior to the catalyst layer deposition. All cathodes were used without further modifications.

Anode material for membrane alkaline water electrolysis

A Ni foam ($2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$) modified by a catalytic layer was used for all measurements. The catalytic layer contained either a PGM-based IrO_2 catalyst (1.5 mg m^{-2}) or non-platinum NiCo_2O_4 (1.5 mg cm^{-2}), and an anion-selective binder PSEMS-CM-DABCO (0.08 mg cm^{-2}). Anode was prepared by sonication dispersion deposition method from catalyst ink containing catalyst, binder and solvent/dispersant (chloroform). Catalyst ink was sonicated for 30 minutes in sonication bath prior to the catalyst layer deposition.

Membrane alkaline water electrolysis

The electrodes were tested in a laboratory membrane alkaline water electrolyser in a two-electrode arrangement. An anion-selective polymer membrane PSEBS-CM-DABCO (TailorMem s.r.o., Czech republic; $60 \mu\text{m}$ thick) was used as a separator of anode and cathode compartments. Details on the membrane properties can be found elsewhere³⁶. The current collectors were made of gold-plated Ni plates. The electrolytic cell body was made of poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK) compressed by duralumin end-plates using a constant torque of 2.5 Nm . The electrolyser was operated in continuous flow-by mode. The volumetric flow rate of liquid solution of catholyte and anolyte each was $25 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$.

The potentiostatic load curves were recorded at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using 0.1 and 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH solutions in the voltage range between 1.5 and 2.0 V (with a step of 0.05 V). Each value of the cell voltage

was maintained for 60 seconds, and the current passing through the cell was recorded. The steady-state values (approx. last 10 seconds) of the current were averaged and used to calculate the current density corresponding to the given cell voltage. Each load curve was measured three times for at least two different samples of the same cathode material to verify data reproducibility. The presented graphs then show the average values of all measurements. The relatively low concentrations of the KOH were chosen with the aim to increase the flexibility of the electrolysis and to test the novel electrode properties at the less strongly alkaline conditions.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was used to separate the ohmic resistance of the cell and the kinetics of the electrode's reactions. The EIS spectra were recorded at a constant cell voltage of 1.8 V . Perturbing signal amplitude of 30 mV and a frequency range of 10 kHz to 0.1 Hz were used. A stability test ($>40 \text{ h}$) was performed in a galvanostatic regime at a current density of 400 mA cm^{-2} in 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH solution at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. To verify the cathode stability even for intermittent electrolysis, the constant polarisation was interrupted every 5 hours for approx. 30 minutes. During the intermission, load curves and EIS spectra were measured to identify the possible degradation processes that might have occurred. Deionised water was supplied to the system during the experiment to maintain a constant electrolyte solution concentration.

Results and discussion

Optimisation of the $\text{xNi}_y\text{Co}_z\text{P}$ catalyst

Mechanism of the catalyst formation is not agreed in detail up to date, but it is clearly a complex process. It is based on the galvanic deposition. The direct deposition of the phosphorous from the aqueous solution was described as abnormal deposition (sometimes also referred as induced co-deposition). It is because elemental phosphorous cannot be directly deposited from aqueous solution, but it can be co-deposited as an alloy in presence of the iron group metals like Ni, Co, Cu etc.^{21, 30}.

In general, the catalytic activity of the multi-atom phosphide-based electrocatalysts is strongly influenced by the catalyst composition (metal to metal or metal to phosphorous atomic ratio etc.)^{19, 28, 37, 38}. Therefore, in the first step, the catalyst optimisation was performed by monitoring the effect of (i) Ni:Co composition and (ii) phosphorous concentration in a deposition solution on the resulting composition of the catalyst, as well as on its electrocatalytic activity towards HER. Since the prepared samples are mostly amorphous, it was not possible to determine the phase composition by XRD. Instead, the SEM-EDS method supported by the XRF and XPS analyses were used to evaluate the elemental composition of the catalyst bulk and surface layer, respectively. XPS analysis additionally allowed to obtain information on chemical state of the elements present. The electrochemical activity was determined by measuring the polarisation curves. From these curves, the Tafel parameters of the materials under study were evaluated.

Influence of the phosphorous concentration in a deposition solution. In the first step, the impact of NaPO₂H₂·H₂O concentration in a catalyst deposition solution was tested. Following concentrations were used: 0.3, 0.6, 0.9 and 1.2 mol dm⁻³. Concentration of the Ni and Co was maintained at 0.2 mol dm⁻³ for both (Ni:Co composition of 0.5). Table 2 shows that the composition of the deposition solution significantly affects the final catalyst composition determined by SEM-EDS. It can be seen that as the concentration of NaPO₂H₂·H₂O increases, the phosphorus content in the catalyst increases almost linearly up to a concentration of 0.9 mol dm⁻³ NaPO₂H₂·H₂O, at which the maximum phosphorus concentration is reached. Further increase in the NaPO₂H₂·H₂O in the synthesis solution did not result in further increase in the phosphorus content in resulting catalyst. Unfortunately, as documented in Figure S1, the varying composition strongly influences the surface morphology of the prepared samples. Areas with varying phosphorous concentration and morphology are present even in the samples obtained using the same initial concentration of NaPO₂H₂·H₂O in the deposition solution, suggesting inhomogeneous deposition of the catalyst. The inhomogeneity of the catalyst increases (reproducibility of the synthesis decreases) with increasing concentration of NaPO₂H₂·H₂O in the deposition solution.

The XRF analysis shows a similar trend regarding the final composition of the catalyst (see Table S1). Differences in absolute values are caused by the higher sensitivity of SEM-EDS to lighter elements, whereas XRF tends to be more sensitive to heavier elements. For this reason, the SEM-EDS analysis was selected for further comparison of catalyst composition, as it is able to determine the amount of phosphorus more accurately. The XPS analysis was performed to obtain additional and more detailed information about the prepared catalyst, such as the elemental composition (Table S2) and oxidation states of the constituting elements in the surface layer. For the initial XPS measurements the 0.2Ni0.2Co0.6P catalyst was used. The XPS survey spectrum of the prepared catalyst (Figure S2) revealed the expected presence of Ni, Co, P, and O. The presence of Na and Cl shown further by XPS, can be attributed to the residues of Na⁺ and Cl⁻, respectively, from the deposition solution.

The deconvoluted high resolution spectra of P 2p, Co 2p, and Ni 2p_{3/2} are shown in

Figure 1. The P 2p spectrum exhibits a main peak at a binding energy of 133.2 eV. This can be attributed to the phosphate species³⁹. The small peak at 129.3 eV corresponds to a

phosphide in CoP and/or NiP^{39,40}. This suggests high degree of surface oxidation, or presence of phosphates. The two additional peaks (124.6 and 122.9 eV) represent the artefact peaks (a.p.) of P-O from the non-monochromatized X-ray source. A non-monochromatized source produces a broader range of X-ray energies, which result in series of artefact peaks of defined intensities and binding energy shifts with respect to the main peak. Such peaks do not correspond to the actual photoelectron signals from the original elements⁴¹.

Deconvolution of the high resolution spectrum of Co 2p is much more complex, as it contains Co in various electronic states, as well as overlapping peak artefacts from non-monochromatized X-rays. Spin orbit splitting between Co 2p_{3/2} and Co 2p_{1/2} spectral lines is about 16 eV. Only Co 2p_{3/2} peaks are discussed here. The main peak at 781.7 eV with a satellite at 785.1 eV correspond to Co-O in Co₃(PO₄)₂, which confirms the oxidation of the catalyst by oxygen⁴². The small peak at 778.5 eV overlapping with the main Co-O peak can be attributed to Co-P^{40,43}. Two additional peaks of plasmon satellites confirming the presence of Co-P should be visible at approx. 781.2 eV and 783 eV. However, they are overlapped by the main Co-O peak and, therefore, cannot be sufficiently distinguished⁴². The last two peaks at 773.4 and 765.3 eV can be attributed to Co Auger peaks⁴⁴.

Due to the even more complex and complicated nature of the Ni 2p spectrum, only the Ni 2p_{3/2} was deconvoluted. Similarly to Co, the main peak at 856.6 eV with a satellite at 862.4 eV can be attributed to Ni²⁺ species in the form of Ni₃(PO₄)₂⁴⁵. The smaller peak at 852.7 eV corresponds to Ni-P^{46,47}. The additional two peaks at lower binding energies represent artefact peaks from the non-monochromatized X-ray source.

To summarise the above analysis, following main substances were identified at the surface of the synthesised catalyst: Co₃(PO₄)₂, Ni₃(PO₄)₂, NiP, CoP. Electrochemical deposition of the phosphorous alloys was referred to be abnormal and induced. Abnormal deposition corresponds to the situation when less noble metal is deposited preferentially, e.g. when Ni and Co are used, less noble Co metal has higher content in the deposited layer. Induced deposition represents the way, how phosphorous can be deposited electrochemically from solution. This is possible only in the presence of the Fe group metals due to the existence of the metal-P bond prior to the deposition. Due to these factors, different compounds can be present in the deposited layer, which agrees with the results observed^{21,30}.

Table 2: Elemental composition (at.%) of the NiCoP catalyst determined by SEM-EDS analysis. Constant Ni:Co composition of 0.5 in the deposition solution (NiCl₂·6H₂O (0.2 mol dm⁻³), CoCl₂·6H₂O (0.2 mol dm⁻³)).

Element	$C_{NaPO_2H_2 \cdot H_2O} / \text{mol dm}^{-3}$			
	0.3	0.6	0.9	1.2
Ni (at.%)	39.7 ± 2.2	42.4 ± 0.5	41 ± 4	36 ± 5
Co (at.%)	53 ± 2	48 ± 1	40 ± 7	47 ± 4
P (at.%)	7.6 ± 0.4	11.1 ± 0.4	18 ± 3	16 ± 9

Figure 1: High resolution spectra (P 2p, Co 2p, and Ni 2p_{3/2}) of the electrodeposited 0.2Ni0.2Co0.6P catalyst (a.p. = artefact peaks). Deposition solution composition: NiCl₂·6H₂O (0.2 mol dm⁻³), CoCl₂·6H₂O (0.2 mol dm⁻³), and NaPO₂H₂·H₂O (0.6 mol dm⁻³); -25 mA cm⁻², 25 °C.

In order to further investigate the influence of the NaPO₂H₂·H₂O concentration on the catalyst surface composition, the comparison of XPS spectra for selected NaPO₂H₂·H₂O concentrations (0.3, 0.6, and 1.2 M) was performed (Figure S3). The corresponding Ni, Co, P, and O spectra do not reveal any significant changes regarding the position of the measured

peaks. This indicates that varying NaPO₂H₂·H₂O concentration does not change the chemical components forming the catalyst produced. Besides, the XPS analysis is also able to provide the concentration (at. %) of the individual elements assuming the homogeneous elemental composition within the surface of samples under study (concentration values of the corresponding elements and a short description of the evaluation is provided in supporting information, see Table S2). While the Ni:Co composition remained close to 1, the phosphorus to metal ratio (determined by XPS) increased from 0.5 to 2.7 with increasing NaPO₂H₂·H₂O concentration. This indicates a greatly increased concentration of phosphorus-containing species on the electrode surface.

These findings raised an interest in finding the influence of the phosphorus concentration on the electrochemical activity of the catalyst produced. To gain this information, polarisation curves were recorded using the RDE (Figure S4) and corresponding Tafel parameters were evaluated (Table 3, Figure S5).

Results obtained show that the increasing concentration of phosphorous has a positive effect on the catalytic activity for the HER. This is in agreement with the literature^{6, 10, 20, 28}, suggesting that the higher content of phosphorous atoms with partially negative charge promotes the weakening of the H–OH bonds in water molecules. This enhances the water dissociation step in the HER mechanism. Therefore, the sample prepared from solution with the 0.9 mol dm⁻³ NaPO₂H₂·H₂O solution (0.2Ni0.2Co0.9P) achieved the lowest overpotential at -10 mA cm⁻². The sample also exhibited the highest apparent exchange current density (*j*₀). This parameter reflects the intrinsic rate of electron transfer between the catalyst and the electrolyte and includes effect of the real electrochemically active surface area. On the other hand, Tafel slope value is related to the reaction mechanism, namely to its rate determining step, and is not influenced by the electrode area. The lowest value of the Tafel slope (*b*) was achieved for the sample with the highest phosphorous concentration in the synthesis solution (0.2Ni0.2Co1.2P), reaching the value of 142 mV dec⁻¹. Theoretically, the maximum value should not exceed 120 mV dec⁻¹ corresponding to the dissociative adsorption of the water molecule on the catalyst surface as a rate determining step. Higher value of the Tafel slope observed indicates rate determining step to be different from the electrochemical one. This can have several reasons, *e.g.* the morphology of the catalyst layer and catalyst itself, which can result in mass transport phenomena in catalyst layer, or contact resistance occurrence between substrate and the catalyst particles. However, such effects should show non-linear part in Tafel curve.

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Table 3: Comparison of evaluated Tafel parameters – Tafel slope (b), overpotential (η) at -10 mA cm^{-2} , and exchange current density (j_0) for catalysts prepared using various concentrations of $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the deposition solution. Ni and Co concentrations 0.2 mol dm^{-3} for both (Ni:Co composition of 0.5)

$c_{\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}} / \text{mol dm}^{-3}$	b / mV dec ⁻¹	η @ -10 mA cm^{-2} / mV	$j_0 / \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$
0.3	161	-541	4.4
0.6	166	-533	6.2
0.9	159	-459	13.0
1.2	142	-461	5.7

The most promising explanation represents non-electrochemical step of the reaction scheme to be rate-determining step of the overall process.

It should be noted that it was not possible to obtain samples with higher bulk phosphorus content than approx. 20 at.%. Moreover, the composition inhomogeneity, even for the same initial concentration of $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, documented by SEM-EDS (Figure S1 and Table S1), caused inconsistency in the measured polarisation curves. Highest variability of the data was observed for the $0.2\text{Ni}0.2\text{Co}1.2\text{P}$. For these reasons, the $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentration of 0.9 mol dm^{-3} was determined as more favourable as it was able to provide a more consistent results than catalyst prepared from 1.2 mol dm^{-3} $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solutions while keeping comparable catalytic activity.

Influence of the Ni:Co composition in a deposition solution. For optimization of the nickel to cobalt ratio (Ni:Co) in synthesis solution, the phosphorous concentration was fixed to 0.6 mol dm^{-3} . Table 4 clearly shows that increasing Ni:Co composition, *i.e.* increasing concentration of $\text{NiCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the deposition solution results in increasing Ni content in the catalyst. Correspondingly, the proportion of Co decreases. Surprisingly,

for the Ni:Co compositions increasing above 0.5, the concentration of phosphorous also increases. This suggests that the phosphorus co-deposition with Ni is more favourable than with Co. This is in agreement with other reported studies showing increased concentrations of phosphorus with increasing Ni:Co compositions^{48,49}.

The varying Ni:Co composition in the deposition solution strongly influences also the surface morphology of the prepared samples (Figure S6). Despite the fact that relative increase in surface area comparing the $0.4\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$ and $0.36\text{Ni}0.04\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$ samples is 180 %, the absolute BET values are still low (see Table 5).

Comparison of XPS spectra with respect to increasing Ni:Co composition in a deposition solution did not reveal any significant changes regarding the position of the recorded peaks (Figure S7). For the initial Ni:Co compositions of 0.1, 0.5, and 0.9 (samples $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$, $0.2\text{Ni}0.2\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$ and $0.36\text{Ni}0.04\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$ respectively) in the deposition solution, the resulting samples exhibited Ni:Co ratios of 0.08, 0.42, and 0.88, respectively (absolute values of corresponding elements are given in Table S3).

Table 4: Elemental composition (at.%) of the $x\text{Ni}y\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$ catalyst determined by SEM-EDS analysis. $\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentration of 0.6 mol dm^{-3} . Total concentration of the Ni and Co compounds 0.4 mol dm^{-3} .

NiCoP (at. %)	composition	Molar concentration of $\text{NiCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in deposition solution						
		0	0.02	0.04	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.36
Ni		0	3.5 ± 0.5	6 ± 3	19 ± 2	42.4 ± 0.5	59 ± 1	64 ± 2
Co		94 ± 2	92.9 ± 0.5	87 ± 6	77 ± 2	48 ± 1	30 ± 1	18.5 ± 1.2
P		6 ± 2	3.7 ± 0.2	7 ± 3	5 ± 1	11.1 ± 0.4	11 ± 1	17.5 ± 0.2

ARTICLE

Table 5: BET surface analysis for selected $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentrations in deposition solution.

$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentration	BET surface area / $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$
0	1.73
0.2	0.95
0.36	3.57

However, the comparison of the peak areas of Ni-O (856.6 eV) and Ni-P (852.7 eV) for varying compositions revealed that as the amount of Ni in the deposition solution increases, the ratio of phosphide Ni to oxidised Ni decreases. Phosphide Ni represented about 37% of the total Ni for the Ni:Co composition of 0.1, but only 5% for the Ni:Co composition of 0.9. This means that although the total phosphorus concentration increased as the Ni:Co composition increases, the concentration of oxidised Ni increased to a greater extent. This is supported by the more pronounced charging of the samples with increased Ni:Co compositions (approx. 3.9 and 4.8 eV for Ni:Co compositions of 0.1 and 0.9, respectively). This indicates reduced electronic conductivity within catalyst due to the increased presence of oxidised species. These factors can potentially negatively affect the electrocatalytic activity of the samples.

The analysis of the Co spectrum revealed a considerable increase in phosphide Co due to the small addition of Ni (from the initial 7% of phosphide Co to 14% for the Ni:Co compositions of 0 and 0.1, respectively). However, further increase in Ni concentration did not have a significant effect, as phosphide Co only increased to 15% and 19% for compositions of 0.5 and 0.9, respectively. This suggests that there may be an optimum amount of Ni in the deposition solution allowing the formation of beneficial phosphide species (low Ni:Co compositions in the deposition solution) and minimising the excessive surface oxidation (such as at high Ni:Co compositions).

The influence of the Ni:Co composition on electrochemical activity was once again determined from the polarisation curves measured on the RDE (Figure S8) and from the evaluated Tafel parameters (Table 6, Figure S9).

The best performance was achieved with Ni:Co composition 0.1 (sample $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$). It is evident that the overall BET surface area (Table 5) was not the main factor influencing the performance of the sample. It is more connected with its catalytic activity. The sample with the highest surface area ($0.36\text{Ni}0.04\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$) exhibited the worst catalytic activity; significantly worse than the sample with the lowest surface area ($0.2\text{Ni}0.2\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$). The explanation of the enhanced activity of the samples with the Ni:Co compositions 0.1 was already

discussed in the above paragraph. A presence of a small amount of Ni ions provided a higher proportion of Ni and Co phosphides on the catalyst surface enhancing the HER. Moreover, for Ni:Co compositions above 0.5, an increasing concentration of oxidised species with sluggish HER activity is present reducing not only the catalyst activity, but also conductivity.

Table 6 shows a gradual increase in Tafel slopes with the increasing Ni:Co composition. The $0.4\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$ sample (Ni:Co composition of 0) exhibited Tafel slope of 120 mV dec^{-1} . This value suggests dissociative water adsorption (Volmer step) is the rate determining step.

Regarding the increasing values of Tafel slope beyond 120 mV dec^{-1} for Ni:Co compositions other than 0, the most probable explanation was proposed by Jakšić et al.⁵⁰, who ascribes the high values of Tafel slope to the presence of oxide species on the catalyst surface. The locally positively charged Ni^{2+} species with more unfilled d-orbitals attract and adsorb OH^- anions preferentially, thereby, blocking the active sites for the adsorption of H atoms⁵¹. This is in agreement with the observations by XPS, where the proportion of Ni-O in the as-prepared material increased with increasing Ni content. Although the Ni:Co composition of 0.1 did not exhibit the lowest value of the Tafel slope, due to the high exchange current density and low overpotential at -10 mA cm^{-2} , this sample can be considered to be the most catalytically active.

Performance of the optimized $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ catalyst. Once the optimal synthesis conditions are known ($\text{NaPO}_2\text{H}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ concentration of 0.9 mol dm^{-3} and Ni:Co composition of 0.1; $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$), it is important to characterise produced catalyst into the detail. Information on catalyst morphology and on the individual elements distribution can be derived from the TEM analysis shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: TEM images (left) and elemental distribution (right) of the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ catalyst particle.

Table 6: Comparison of evaluated Tafel parameters – Tafel slope (b), overpotential (η) at -10 mA cm^{-2} , and exchange current density (j_0) for selected Ni:Co composition in the deposition solution (total concentration of Ni and Co 0.4 mol dm^{-3}).

Ni:Co composition / -	$b / \text{mV dec}^{-1}$	$\eta @ -10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2} / \text{mV}$	$j_0 / \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$
0	120	-483	0.9
0.05	159	-479	9.7
0.1	149	-430	13.0
0.25	152	-470	8.1
0.5	169	-534	6.9
0.75	170	-533	7.3
0.9	171	-570	4.6

It is clear that the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ catalyst maintains the same amorphous structure as the previous samples. Ni, Co, and P elements are homogeneously distributed in the particle. The lower intensity of Ni in the catalyst is in agreement with its low content determined by SEM-EDS showing that the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.6\text{P}$ catalyst contains 6.2 at.% of Ni, 80.5 at.% of Co, and 13.3 at.% of P. The observed composition fits to the previous trends showing the content of phosphorous to be dependent not only of the phosphorous, but of the content of Ni in synthesis solution, too.

Figure 3, Figure S10 and Table 7 show the comparison of the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ with the most active samples from the previous sections, as well as with the bare glassy carbon electrode and Pt/C catalyst. It is evident that the optimised catalyst exhibits significantly higher catalytic activity than the

Figure 3: Comparison of the polarisation curves of the selected samples.

Experimental conditions: Working RDE (500 rpm, 0.2 mg cm^{-2}), reference RHE, Ni counter electrode, 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KOH, $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $0-10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, $50 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, iR corrected.

other samples. It achieved the lowest overpotential of -363 mV at -10 mA cm^{-2} and the highest exchange current density of $27.8 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. This suggests that the composition optimisation proved to be successful and provided the most active sample. When compared to the Pt/C catalyst, the performance of the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ catalyst is significantly lower.

Such observation is not surprising due to the facts that Pt represents one of the most active catalyst for HER and catalyst loads of $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ and Pt/C in this case were the same. However, utilization of Pt as catalyst in industrial water electrolyzers is limited by its price. Cheaper non-Pt catalyst can be used in higher loads compensating thus lower activity. The optimised catalyst was, therefore, selected for the preparation of the modified Ni foam cathode and for further testing in a membrane alkaline water electrolyser. It was compared with performance of the Pt/C catalyst as a state-of-the-art catalyst. In the case of the glassy carbon electrode two Tafel slopes were observed (Figure S10, Table 7). At low current densities, the Tafel slope and overpotentials at 10 mA cm^{-2} were lower when compare to the values evaluated for high current density region.

Performance of the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}/\text{NF}$ cathode under the AMWE conditions

Load curve measurement. The performance of the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ catalyst deposited on Ni foam ($0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}/\text{NF}$) for the HER in an alkaline environment was determined in a membrane alkaline water electrolyser. Three samples differing in the amount of catalyst deposited on the Ni foam were tested. The catalyst loading was controlled by the deposition time as shown in Table 8.

ARTICLE

Table 7: Comparison of evaluated Tafel parameters – Tafel slope (b), overpotential (η) at -10 mA cm^{-2} , and exchange current density (j_0) for the selected materials. For glassy carbon electrode two slopes were evaluated due to change of the reaction mechanism.

Catalyst	$b / \text{mV dec}^{-1}$	$\eta @ -10 \text{ mA cm}^{-2} / \text{mV}$	$j_0 / \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$
0.04Ni0.36Co0.9P	142	-363	27.8
0.04Ni0.36Co0.6P	149	-430	13.0
0.2Ni0.2Co0.9P	159	-459	13.0
Glassy carbon	131/265	-607/-679	0.2/27.4
Pt/C	47	-79	480

In order to investigate the distribution of the catalyst within the porous electrode volume for selected electrodeposition times, SEM-EDS mapping of the electrode cross-section was carried out, as shown in Figure S11. The images revealed that the catalyst is distributed within the entire electrode volume for all electrodeposition times. The highest loading is observed at the surface facing the counter electrode during deposition procedure, especially in the case of phosphorus. From the increase in the total mass of the deposited catalyst, as shown in Table 8, it can be concluded that the thickness of the deposited catalyst layer increases with longer electrodeposition times. However, it is clearly seen that the amount of 0.04Ni0.36Co0.9P catalyst deposited per time unit decreases with the higher deposition time. This can be explained by increased share of the current consumed for HER instead of the deposition of the additional catalyst.

Table 8: Electrodeposition times and the corresponding catalyst loadings of the 0.04Ni0.36Co0.9P deposition.

Deposition time / min	Catalyst loading / mg cm^{-2}
1	1.45
15	6.57
30	10.68

To investigate the cathode performance for the AMWE, various measurements, including load curves, EIS, and stability test, were conducted in a single-cell membrane alkaline electrolyser. In order to eliminate, to the highest possible extent, the effect of the anodic reaction on the experimental data, IrO₂ was used as an OER anode catalyst for these measurements. Figure S12 shows the load curves in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ and 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH. In both KOH solutions, the electrode obtained after 15 min of deposition time exhibited the best performance, which was comparable with the performance of cathode containing 0.4 mg Pt cm⁻². The detailed description of the effect of the deposition time is given in supporting information related to Figure S12.

For the stability test, non-platinum NiCo₂O₄ oxygen evolution catalyst was used to show the performance of the AMWE without the platinum-based catalysts.

The influence of the anode catalyst on the AMWE performance and corresponding discussion are provided in SI, see Figure S13. The durability of the 0.04Ni0.36Co0.9P/NF cathode for intermittent electrolysis was determined in a 42 h long stability test. Figure 4A shows the average values of the cell voltage for individual 5 h periods and the full cell voltage record. The sample exhibited remarkable stability in the time interval under study. The overall cell voltage insignificantly increased with the slope of 0.04 mV h⁻¹.

Figure 4: Intermittent stability test performed under AMWE conditions. Average values of the cell voltage at constant current density of 250 mA cm⁻² and complete progress of the stability test (A); load curves evaluated during the stability test (B).

Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; cathode (4 cm²) – 0.04Ni0.36Co0.9P/NF (15 min); anode (4 cm²) – 1.5 mg NiCo₂O₄ cm⁻² + 0.08 mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm⁻²; 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH electrolyte; temperature – 50 °C.

Overall, the electrolytic cell performance remained exceptionally stable during the stability test. The load curves measured at the beginning of the experiment and after 10 hours showed a substantial increase in the achieved current densities for all applied voltages (Figure 4B). Observed improvement of AMWE performance is due to the initial activation of the catalysts and conditioning of both the anion-selective separator and catalytic layer binder.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy characterisation.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data are typically evaluated by means of equivalent circuit. Its structure must be based on a relevant model consideration and each element has defined physical meaning corresponding to the monitored system. Helpful tool for this analysis represents the distribution of relaxation times (DRT) method. DRT method is based on deconvoluting the spectrum and determining characteristic times indicating kinetics of each determined process⁵².

Figure 5A shows the Nyquist plot of a typical experimentally obtained EIS data (circle symbols). From the depressed two semicircles it is difficult to determine number of the characteristic times present and in consequence to propose adequate equivalent electrical circuit. Figure 5B shows the results of the DRT analysis of the experimentally obtained data. Peaks in the Figure 5B suggest presence of the four time-constants. The time constant at frequency 2160 Hz was, however, not defined well enough to be evaluated with sufficient accuracy. For this reason, positions of the three frequencies corresponding to the time constant evaluated in the next steps of the EIS analysis are shown in Figure 5A.

Based on the results of the DRT analysis, corresponding equivalent circuit (Figure 6) was proposed containing three time-constants. The structure of the equivalent circuit was chosen based on the fact that whereas two of the constants are clearly cell voltage dependent, the third one not dependence (see Figure S15). This situation was handled already before by Lasia⁵³ and other authors^{54,55} and was explained by impact of the porous structure of the electrode. An alternative explanation can lie in the presence of additional ionically conducting layer on the substrate⁵⁶.

Figure 5: Nyquist plot showing points measured by EIS (circle symbol), frequencies corresponding to the time constant and fit of the measured points (A); results of the DRT analysis of the Nyquist plot (B).

Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; anode (4 cm²) – 1.5 mg NiCo₂O₄ cm⁻² + 0.08 mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm⁻²; 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH electrolyte; temperature – 50 °C, amplitude – 30 mV, frequency range – 10 kHz to 0.1 Hz.

In the referred works, however, experiments were performed in 3-electrode arrangement with well-defined system. In the present case, two porous electrodes modified with catalyst layers are analysed. Despite the significant effort, it was not possible to find any work describing and explaining in more details behaviour of such system. Therefore, the circuit proposed here is modified to a certain degree to reflect this fact. The inductance L arises from the physical layout and construction of electrical components and wiring. Resistance $R(\text{cell})$ refers to the overall ohmic resistance of the assembled cell and connected cables. Constant phase elements $\text{CPE}_{1,2}$ describes the double-layer capacitance at the electrode-electrolyte interface for both, anode and cathode. Polarisation resistances $R(\text{p}1)$ and $R(\text{p}2)$ correspond once again to the polarisation resistances of both electrodes. Elements $R(\text{morph})$ and $\text{CPE}(\text{morph})$ describe the influence of electrodes morphology.

Generally, it is not possible to address specifically R_p values to anode or cathode reaction, but in the literature, anodic oxygen evolution reaction is typically considered to be slower with higher R_p value when compared to the cathodic hydrogen evolution reaction rate. In this study this issue was solved performing experiments utilizing two different anodes (IrO_2 vs. NiCo_2O_4). Under the general assumption that OER represents the reaction with higher $R(\text{p})$ value, $R(\text{p}1)$ represents polarisation resistance of OER with characteristic frequency (23 ± 1.6) Hz, while $R(\text{p}2)$ corresponds to the polarisation resistance of HER with characteristic frequency (4.7 ± 0.8) Hz for cell voltage 1.8 V. Results are provided in SI (Figure S13–15) with corresponding discussion.

Figure 6: Equivalent circuit used to evaluate the ohmic resistance ($R(\text{cell})$), and polarisation resistances ($R(\text{p}1)$ and $R(\text{p}2)$).

The evaluated EIS parameters at 1.8 V during stability test confirm high stability of the prepared $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ catalyst and the whole electrolysis cell, see Figure 7. EIS results show negligible changes in the $R(\text{cell})$ and $R(\text{morph})$ values. In the case of the $R(\text{p})$ values, it is possible to see decrease for $R(\text{p}1)$ within the first 20 hours, which can be explained by the catalyst activation. Value $R(\text{p}2)$ rather fluctuates around the stable value (0.34 ± 0.05) $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$. Results of EIS thus confirm the stability of the $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}$ catalyst.

Figure 7: EIS results of intermittent stability test performed under AMWE conditions.

Experimental conditions: separator – PSEBS-CM-DABCO; cathode (4 cm^2) – $0.04\text{Ni}0.36\text{Co}0.9\text{P}/\text{NF}$ (15 min); anode (4 cm^2) – $1.5 \text{ mg NiCo}_2\text{O}_4 \text{ cm}^{-2} + 0.08 \text{ mg PSEBS-CM-DABCO cm}^{-2}$; $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KOH}$ electrolyte; temperature – $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, amplitude – 30 mV , frequency range – 10 kHz to 0.1 Hz . (No pre-treatment was applied.)

Conclusions

The cathodic electrodeposition from solution proved to be a facile and simple method to prepare active NiCoP HER catalyst with amorphous structure. Optimisation of deposition solution was proven to have a significant impact on the composition and, subsequently, also on the catalytic activity of the prepared catalysts. The higher concentration of phosphorus could enhance water dissociation, whereas the optimal Ni:Co composition provided a highest proportion of catalytically active Ni and Co phosphides phase in the material.

In the case of catalyst deposition directly on the porous substrate, deposition time was found to be another important parameter. The main reason was catalyst distribution within the porous electrode structure. The short electrodeposition time (1 min) did not allow to deposit a sufficient amount of catalyst. On the contrary, the longer deposition time (30 min) provided a too high local catalyst loading resulting in mass transport limitation apparent especially at high cell voltages. The best AMWE performance was achieved using cathode obtained after 15 minutes of electrodeposition. In less concentrated KOH solution, the AMWE possessing cathode outperformed even the Ni foam modified by state-of-the-art Pt/C catalyst, achieving a current density of 361 mA cm^{-2} versus 321 mA cm^{-2} at 2 V, respectively. Application of the distribution of relaxation times analysis allowed to separate polarization resistances of both main electrode reactions from electrochemical impedance spectra providing thus kinetic information for both electrodes under the conditions of the alkaline water electrolysis.

The EIS analysis of the results obtained has proven, that distribution of relaxation time represents very helpful, and may

be necessary, tool to analyse the spectra obtained. Significant work needs to be done here to understand the alkaline water electrolysis process more into the detail and to allow reliable analysis of the experimental data.

Author contributions

Jaromír Hnát – data curation, methodology, supervision, visualisation, writing – review & editing; **Martin Ďurovič** – investigation, visualisation, writing – original draft; **Tomas Bystron** – formal analysis, writing – review & editing; **Magdalena Strečková** – funding acquisition, resources, writing – review & editing; **Karel Bouzek** – conceptualization, funding acquisition, supervision, writing – review & editing

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data availability

A data availability statement (DAS) is required to be submitted alongside all articles. Please read our [full guidance on data availability statements](#) for more details and examples of suitable statements you can use.

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